

INVITRO-MICROPROPAGATION OF VIRUS-FREE GUAVA (*Psidium guajava* L.) PLANTLETS THROUGH MERISTEM CULTURE TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Standardization of protocol for in vitro cloning of virus-free micropropagation of Guava plantlets through meristem culture was carried out using the stock plant of guava maintained at shade net house (75% shade) and pruned severely to encourage new growth about 3cm long shoots were excised and defoliated. The explants were pretreated in solution containing 0.1% carbendazim and 100mg/L PVP for 1 hour and then washed with Twenty-20 wetting agent. The pretreated explants were further treated with Hgcl 0.1% for 5 minutes aseptically followed by thorough washing in autoclaved distilled water. The sterilized explants were cultured on MS medium supplemented with BAP (3.0 mg/L) for shoot bud induction and proliferation. The proliferated shoots were then sub cultured on MS medium containing 10mg/L IBA for rhizogenesis. The rooted plants were finally shifted to autoclaved coconut husk fortified with ½ MS salt mixture for acclimatization. The in vitro plantlets after rooting were acclimatized in jiffy pots and established in the soil.

KEYWORDS: Invitro, micropropagation, virus-free, guava, plantlets, meristem culture, technique.

INTRODUCTION

Plant tissue culture techniques have become a powerful tool for studying and solving food insecurity problems in Nigeria. Micro propagation and ;in vitro techniques have become more widely used in commercial horticulture and agriculture for the mass propagation of crop plants George *et al.*, (1984).

Clonal propagation of guava through micro propagation has been demonstrated using shoot tip and nodal segments (Amin and Jaiswal 1987). Guava propagation by layering, inarching, and budding is achievable. A unique technique of patch budding of guava scions demonstrated at the horticultural experiment center appears commercially feasible (Mortan 1987). Several clonal methods including rooting of succulent green wood, forked or patch budding, air layering. Layering and inarching for propagating guava germ plasm have been discussed by Chandra (1965) and Samson (1986). Micro propagation of guava has been achieved by single node cuttings from seedlings raised in green house, in vitro raised seedlings Ali, *et al.* (2003). And shoot tip explants from mature trees Amin & Jaiswal 1987).

Tissue culture is an efficient technique combined with conventional methods, for clonal propagation of guava and applied with the object of enhancing the rate of multiplication. (Loh & Rao, 1989). Over a million plants can be obtained from a small portion of explant shoot tip within few months. Such a prolific rate of multiplication cannot be expected by any of the in vivo methods of clonal propagation. (Ali *et al* 2007).

The major agronomic and horticultural problems facing the guava industry are severity of wilt disease and susceptibility to many pathogens and stresses, low yield and short fruit shelf life high seed content e.t,c Rai *et al* (2007). Conventional breeding techniques have limited scope of improvement of guava owing to long juvenile period, self incompatibility and heterozygous nature. Conventional propagation methods, i.e grafting and stool layering, suitable for improvement of guava already exist, but due to the long juvenile period they are time consuming and cumbersome Jaiswal and Amin, (1992). Propagation from seeds is not practical because they germinate poorly and unevenly and long time is required for seedling emergence (Doijode, 2001). Micro propagation could resolve some of the most serious problems of the guava industry.

Plant tissue culture technique could play pivotal role in improving the quality and production of fruit micro-propagation is rapid, efficient and cost effective. Additionally it will help in germ plasm preservation genetic improvement and true to type plants can be produced year round for the market and growers by utility of this technique. The present was carried out to produce virus-free Guava plantlet which allows for expedient multiplication of micro plants that are easily established *ex vitro* through meristem culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of Medium

The nutrient media contained inorganic and organic constituent according to Murashige and Skoog (M&S, 1962). The inorganic constituent were KNO₃ 1900ml, MgSO₄.7H₂O 370ml, CaCl₂.2H₂O 440ml, NH₄NO₃ 165ml, KH₂ PO₄ 170ml, FeSO₄. 2H₂O 27.8ml, MnSO₄ 22.3ml, KI 0.83ml, CaCl₂.6H₂O 0.025ml. The organic constituent were: glycine 2ml, myo-inositol 100ml, thiamine-HCl 0.1ml, pyridoxine – HCl 0.5ml, nicotinic acid 0.5ml, agar 8% W/V and Sucrose 3% W/V. Auxins, kinetin and gibberellic acid were also added to the Murashige and Skoog medium in different concentrations and combinations. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 5.7 with either 1N KOH or 1N HCl. The culture media were autoclave at 15 lb/in² at 121°C for 15 minutes, then maintain at 27± 2°C in the culture room.

SOURCE OF PLANT MATERIALS

Plant materials required for the experiments were obtained from stock plant of guava which was maintained at shade net house (75% shade) and pruned severely to encourage new growth. About 30cm long shoots were excised and defoliated.

SURFACE STERILIZATION OF EXPLANTS

The shoots were first washed under running tap water and then kept in a solution containing 0.1% carbendazim (Bavistin) +25mg/L Rifampicin and two drops of Tween-20 for one hour. After thorough washing the explants were surface sterilized with 0.1% HgCl₂ for 6 minutes aseptically followed by 5 – 6 washing with sterile distilled water.

INOCULATION OF EXPLANTS ON MEDIUM

The processed explants were inoculated on MS medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) in different concentrations and combinations. The PH of the medium was adjusted to 5.7 with either 1N KOH or 1N HCl. The culture media were autoclaved at 15 lb/in² at 121°C for 15 minutes, then maintained at 27± 2°C in the culture room.

ACCLIMATIZATION OF EXPLANTS

The plants were shifted to shade net house (50%) provided with misting. The caps of the bottles were loosened gradually and the plants were shifted to pots. The data on acclimatization was recorded after 45 days after root initiation.

INDEXING FOR VIRUS

A serological identification was conducted in the cultured plants and to detected virus. In this detection the double antibody sandwich enzyme-linked immuno absorbent assay (DAS-ELISA) methods were followed. Virus free plantlets were used for mass propagation in MS with hormone supplements were used. The mass propagation was evaluated by number of shoot and root formation, shoot length and root formation frequency. Once the plants showed stability, they were shifted to field during the months of July – August. The observations were recorded periodically and the data was subjected to statistical analysis using completely randomized design.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stock plant of guava was maintained in shade net house (75% shading) and was sprayed frequently with fungicidal solution (0.1% Bavestine + Twenty – 20) followed by sterilization with HgCl₂ for 6 minutes aseptically.

As shown in Table 1, the best hormone combination among the treatments to produce plantlets was 0.1mg/L GA₃. The medium did not induce organ formation from guava callus at any given level of hormone combinations. However, callus could be maintained at a longer period in the medium when fortified with a mixture at a longer period in the medium when fortified with a mixture of amino acid and vitamins.

As shown in Table 2, shoots obtained from the proliferation stage were rooted on half – strength MS medium containing indole butyric acid and alpha – naphthalene – acetic acid. MS medium showed quick establishment of meristem in culture media. Meristem culture is a unique technique to free from various pathogens including viruses, viroides, mycoplasma, bacteria and fungi. Walkey (1978).

Confirmation of virus elimination in meristem derive plant sample by DAS-ELISA test: Before mass micropropagation meristems derive plantlets were tested for virus detection by DAS-ELISA techniques. Virus free plantlets were used for mass micropropagation.

Field performance of meristem derived plantlets: The on field performance of meristem derived plants shows, morphological characters of meristem derived plants were found normal, varieties stability was also recorded among the meristem derived guava plants.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, visual observation of the plants shows that, no symptoms of viral disease were noticed fruit (Guava) yield of meristem derived plant was more than that of derived plants. Since good plant health is major advantage in the development

Of elite mother (Stock material) production of virus free/disease free micropropagation offers many advantages over conventional method of plant.

RECOMMENDATION

In recommendation, Guava produce through micropropagation (artificial seeds) can be easily exploited on a large scale, generating millions of plants in few days, and these may become a profitable multibillion rupees industry in near future, if this technique is employed as a means of disease free/virus free Guava production in the study area.

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Table 1: Hormones in different concentration and combinations in the modified M&S medium.

CONCENTRATION OF GROWTH REGULATORS (Mg/L)			
TREATMENT	2, 4 – D	BA	GA ₃
1	0.5	0.10	0.1
2	1.0	0.25	0.1
3	1.5	0.40	0.1
4	2.0	1.00	0.1
5	2.0	1.00	0.1
6	2.5	1.50	0.1
7	1.0	0.10	0.2
8	1.0	0.20	0.2
9	1.5	0.40	0.2
10	2.5	1.50	0.2
11	0.5	0.10	0.1
12	1.0	0.20	0.1
13	1.5	0.30	0.1
14	2.0	0.60	0.1
15	2.5	1.50	0.1

2, 4 – D: 2, 4 – Dichlorophenoxy acetic acid , BA: Benzyl adenine, GA₃: Gibbrellic acid , KN: Kinetin , BAP: 6 – Benzyl amino purine.

Table 2. EFFECT OF MEDIA CONCENTRATION AND IBA ON ROOTS FORMATION BY MERISTEM CULTURED GUAVA

IBA (Mg/L)	Days taken for rooting	Number of root	Length of root (cm)	Weight of root (g)
Half MS + 2.5 IBA	30.0	1.32	1.966	0.0047
Half MS + 5.0 IBA	34.32	1.33	3.017	0.0067
Half MS + 10.0 IBA	29.67	1.33	2.283	0.0051
Half MS + 25.0 IBA	29.33	2.00	2.960	0.0058
Full MS + 2.5 IBA	22.33	2.33	2.950	0.0089
Full MS + 5.0 IBA	23.33	2.33	1.890	0.0077
Full MS 10.0 IBA	17.67	3.0	6.750	0.0211
Full MS + 25.0 IBA	30.67	2.33	1.523	0.0080
Full MS + 0.0 IBA	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.0000
SEN±	0.220	0.36	0.0	2.0
CD (0.05)	0.45	0.74	0.0	4.12

IBA = 6 – Benzyl amino purine

MS = Murashige and Skoog

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